

CREATIVITY OF GAFUR GULAM IN THE POINT OF YOUNG LAWYER**Bakhromova Laylo Rayim qizi****Tashkent state university of law****Faculty of public law 2 year****Winner of the Minister of Justice scholarship****laylorayimovna@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728357>**

Annotation: This article presents the legal analysis of Gafur Ghulam's works, his role in law-making and the ideas supporting the education of young people put forward in his works. Also, through the analysis of literary critical articles of the writer, attention is paid to the shortcomings existing in the society today. It was said that the study of our national heritage is important in training qualified legal personnel.

Key words: "Yodgor", "Naughty boy", legal consciousness, legal culture, legal idealism, legal neglect, state policy regarding youth, work of minors, women's rights, children's rights, fraud, theft.

The Uzbek people have long loved literature, loved poetry, and cherished the legacy of creative writers. Such writers lived and created in our country that there is hardly a person who did not know them and did not enjoy their works. Gafur Ghulam is one of such great writers, the owner of a sharp pen.

Gafur Ghulam's childhood coincided with the cold war period, the poet was orphaned by his parents early, he was the eldest of four orphans, he had to see the difficulties of life and taste the fists of life. Gafur Ghulam's father was literate, spoke Uzbek, Tajik and Russian languages and wrote poems under the pseudonyms Mirza and Gafur. It would not be an exaggeration to say that Gafur Ghulam was in the circle of writers and calligraphers from Tashkent, Khyslat, Shamurod, and poets from Fergana, Asiri, Muqimi, Furqat, and Muhiylar, which made his talent in the literary. After all, the treasures left by the poet have high value and importance in the life of the society. Therefore, it is not in vain that it is said that "Even if poets pass away, their works are a mirror that speaks of the poet's life."

Studying Gafur Ghulam's work is still important today. In particular, the writer's works are relevant from a legal point of view, and are important in developing the legal consciousness and legal culture of society members, in providing solutions to violations arising in various fields of law, and in strengthening the highest level of human interests. In addition, to educate the young generation, in whose hands the future of our country is, with a sense of patriotism, to appreciate our sacred gift - independence by studying the difficult history of our people, to make a worthy contribution to the establishment of a democratic state, and to fulfill their civic duties diligently. acts as a support.

It should be mentioned here that in the author's work, we can see issues related to family-legal, civil-legal relations, and criminal law. Also, his literary and critical articles (Collection of Perfect Works, Volume 11) reveal the flaws that have existed in society since ancient times. While reading the unbiased images of that time, through thinking and comparisons, we can see the reforms that have been implemented and should be

implemented in the state administration system of our country, the system of law-enforcement bodies (law enforcement agencies), and law-making.

Therefore, below we will analyze the legal issues covered in the works of Gafur Ghulam:

The short story "Yodgor" was written in 1936, and it is distinguished by its socio-educational importance, as well as the fact that it covers current topics related to family law. The hero of the story considered the opinion that "Every girl who wants to be happy in the future should study" and in the image of Saodat, the place of women in society and the importance of the concept of gender equality were shown in the story. The story begins with the scene of divorce, and the reader knows that the characters of the work will have a negative impact on their future life: By colluding in advance, using the identity document of another person through fraud, easily deceiving the officers of the bodies that write civil status documents. He achieved his bad goals, and hands the baby over to a stranger, which causes the honor, dignity and reputation of the teenager to be damaged, and the future of the baby is dark. If we look at this problematic situation in today's interpretation, first of all, there have been very big positive changes in the register RCSD system and reforms are ongoing.

A single electronic archive of RCSD has been created, which allows the population to quickly obtain archival references and information of the registry office. As a result of the full operation of the electronic archive, not a few days, but certain minutes are spent on obtaining the necessary information.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the activities of judicial bodies and institutions in the implementation of the state legal policy", starting from July 1, 2018, coordination of the practice of law enforcement, methodical provision of the activity of civil status registration bodies, "unified electronic system of the RCSD" "archive" information system, the tasks of management of its regional archives were entrusted to the State Services Agency under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, registry authorities were transferred to the authorities of districts (cities) and a system of continuous analysis of work in this field was established.

Accordingly, in order to prevent ambiguities that may arise in practice, the scope of obligations and responsibilities of officials responsible for recording civil status documents, i.e. district (city) mayors, chairmen of women's committees, directors of the State Services Agency, heads of district (city) registry offices clearly defined.

The children's rights of Yodgor, one of the main characters of the story "Yodgor", remain a topic of discussion both before and now. At that time, alimony, child's education, growing up in a healthy environment were satisfied only with the love of family members. At this point, it is appropriate to pay attention to the extent to which children's rights have been reformed. In 1989, the Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted by the UN, which defined four areas (survival, development, protection and ensuring the rights of children to participate in decision-making directly related to them). Enshrined in the laws of Uzbekistan. For example, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has a chapter

on separate family relations (it is important that this chapter is not included in the constitutions of other countries) and it states that parents are obliged not only to support their children until they reach adulthood, but also to educate them. In addition, "On the guarantees of children's rights", "On the state policy regarding youth", "On the human rights representative of the Supreme Assembly (OMBUDSMAN)", "On the support of breastfeeding and food products for infants and young children on requirements", "On preschool education and upbringing", "On amendments and additions to certain legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the establishment of additional guarantees of children's rights.

Another famous short story created by the poet in 1936 is "Shum bola". The work describes the life of Tashkent in the twentieth century. If this work is read from the point of view of a lawyer, one can notice the writer's legal views and his contribution to the legal culture of the members of the society. On the eve of the Second World War, not only Uzbekistan, but also the countries under the political control of the Soviet power in Central Asia, the image of that period, political processes, unemployment, poverty and the consequences of its occurrence are covered.

In the image of a single mother in the play, the attention paid to mothers, women and children and the violation of their rights can be seen as the reason for the non-existence of the rights of mothers and children. The main character of the play is caught in the trap of persons with negative behavior and the work forced and imposed on him by adults. In addition, the involvement of a minor child in hard labor, his daily beatings, on the one hand, the attitude towards the young generation, who is considered the future of the nation, on the other hand, is a clear proof that the work of minors is not protected. Due to lack of knowledge, he became involved in petty hooliganism, theft, and fraud.

Today, our state pays great attention to the policy of minors. Conditions are being created for their education, Article 41 of our Constitution states that everyone has the right to free compulsory education, the adoption of the Law "On Education" on September 23, 2020, juvenile offenders neighborhood, we can give an example of the policy of our state in order to provide all-round assistance to the children of families who have lost their breadwinners, are in need of support, and have entered the iron book, to be sponsored by the Youth Affairs Agency.

His literary-critical article entitled "Gathering young forces" begins with the thought that "we have many young forces and talented people lying around." Through the article, the writer invites young people to gather together, show their talents to the public and support them. He also tries to show how important their education and upbringing.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to strengthen our legislation and fill in its shortcomings, great attention is being paid to the use of foreign experiences, which will certainly bring positive results. However, it is possible to change the legislation and the legal system for the better by reading the works inherited by our great writers and our ancestors, without being limited to one side. After all, in their works, the difficulties and shortcomings of our people are clearly highlighted. Then, it will be easier to implement

legislation that does not harm our mentality and the traditions of our people. In addition, it ensures the implementation of populist laws that are compatible with the people's lifestyle and increases the legal awareness of citizens. Therefore, the importance of education in the prevention of crime is high, because the application of legal norms to every case leads to legal idealism or legal neglect, which causes the violation of the legal system.

At this point, I would like to mention that our educational institution supports the study of Gafur Ghulam's work as one of the main means of training qualified legal personnel.

REFERENCES:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent. "Uzbekistan". 2022.
2. "Xalq so'zi" 19.11.2020.online edition
3. Theory of state and law. Textbook. Tashkent. "Justice". 2018. Page 275.
4. Selected works of Gafur Ghulam. Tashkent. Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam. 2021.
5. A collection of perfect works. The eleventh roof. Literary-critical articles. Uzbekistan SSR. "Fan" publishing house. 1989. Page 11.